

ISic1098

I.Sicily inscription 1098

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Marsala

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140581

1. Φλάουιον Ι [— — —]
2. [—] φιλόσο[φον ά]-
3. [π]ὸ κολωνείας [Φλ]-
4. αουίας ΑΙΤ [— — —]
5. C Κωνστα [ντ— — —]
6. [—]ΦΙΛΗΜC [— — —]
7. οί Λιλυ [βαῖοι — —]
8. [— —]ΠΟ [— — — —]
9. [— —].Ο [— — — —]
10. [— —]Η[— — — — π]-
11. ᾄσι μόν [ος— —]
12. [—]Π [Λιλ]υβαίων |
13. [ᾄνδ]ρα σοφόν [—]
14. [—] κλέος ᾄν [δρῶν]
- 15.
16. [— —]ΚΑΛΛΤΝ [— — —]
17. [— — —]ΦΙΛΟCΟ [— —]
18. [— — — —]ΗΠΟΛ [— —]
- 19.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492719

EDCS 39102255

PHI 140581

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0278 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Cagnat, R., Toutain, J., Jouguet, P. 1906-1927. *Inscriptiones Graecae ad res Romanas pertinentes.* Paris. At 500

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic1098. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385481>